

DISASTER RISK AND COMMUNITY VULNERABILITY ASSESSMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF LOCAL EARLY WARNING SYSTEMS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article has been prepared in the field of development of multi-hazard early warning systems and consideration of risk and vulnerability assessment to natural disasters of the population living in remote areas of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Particular attention is paid to the relevance of assessment of the population needs and their ability to respond effectively to disaster risks when developing a strategy to provide communities with the necessary types and means of early warning systems. Current trends in the development of the four main components of multi-hazard early warning systems are reviewed, with a focus on the first and fourth, including disaster risk assessment and the ability of the population to respond to early warning messages.*

Keywords: *multi-hazard early warning system; disaster risk assessment; vulnerability; adaptability, readiness, modelling; natural hazards forecasting; community-based early warning systems; alert; disaster-prone areas.*

Introduction

The Republic of Uzbekistan is the most densely populated country in Central Asia with a population of more than 37.5 million people living on an area of 448,924 square kilometers, which is approximately 87 people per 1 square kilometer. This factor is important when considering the vulnerability of the population to distinct types of threats, both natural and manufactured. Unfortunately, the climatic and geographical features of the country result in an increased risk of natural disasters such as floods, mudslides and landslides, avalanches, droughts, the number, and scale of which have increased significantly due to climate change. At the same time, Uzbekistan is located in one of the seismically dangerous zones with the probability of strong earthquakes of magnitude up to 8-9 on the Richter scale. In Uzbekistan, natural disasters affect an average of 1.4 million people each year and cause almost US\$ 3 billion in damages. Expert estimate that a major flood could cost the economy about 5 per cent of GDP, and a severe drought would have equally serious economic consequences [1].

Considering the existing threats to the population safety, it is necessary to ensure early warning to prevent and take emergency protection measures. In this case, the key role should be given to the creation of an effective warning system, taking to account multi-hazard approach to various types of possible threats of disaster. In this regard, Uzbekistan has found climate change adaptation as a priority, emphasizing the need to prove the existing Multi-Hazard Early Warning System (MHEWS) to alert the population to the risks of emergencies.

Multi-Hazard Early Warning Systems is an international term defined by the United Nations, which means the dissemination of information to the population through local networks

about hazards arising from the threat or occurrence of disasters, allowing the population to take emergency measures to reduce the risk of disasters [2]. It notes a comprehensive approach to early warning of hazards, which includes four main components linked to each other, including:

Regular collection and exchange of disaster risk data, disaster risk assessment.

Regular monitoring of hazards and their consequences.

Effective early warning systems for hazards and threats that distribute prompt, correct and adequate warning signals.

Readiness of population to response to forecasts and emergency warnings.

The development of Multi-Hazard Early Warning System involves the creation of mainly automated hydrometeorological observation systems (ground-based, radar and satellite), coupled with data collection and transmission systems using modern means of communication, automatic processing of observation data and issuance of forecasts, prompt delivery of forecast information to various consumers, primarily the population. The MHEWS should ensure 100% coverage of the population living in the disaster-prone areas, including people with disabilities, considering the differentiation by type of disability, as well as the gender aspect [3]. In turn, the experience of eliminating disasters and their consequences has clearly demonstrated that the prompt response of forces, timely warning and informing the population can significantly reduce material losses and the number of victims.

However, these events have revealed a number of problems with warning systems, one of which is that centralized warning systems mainly cover the population of cities and district centers, while in rural areas, as well as in mountainous and foothill areas, such systems are either insufficient or the majority of the population does not use them and not informed of their existence. Unfortunately, the level of preparedness of the population for emergency situations is still very low. People do not trust information, do not respond to warnings, do not believe in an unfavorable development of situation, and refuse to leave their places until the last moment.

This is why, to develop an effective early warning system, one of the important elements is the need to conduct a qualitative vulnerability and capacity assessment of local communities to existing disaster hazards and risks, which will ultimately determine the strategy for further actions to ensure that early warning systems reach all categories of the population. This measure is also necessary to identify unaccounted sectors of disaster exposure that have not been previously considered and that can only be identified through an assessment based on research conducted directly in the target areas and with the participation of community residents.

Materials and Methods

The goal of the research is to examine the need to use the first component of an early warning system as a disaster risk assessment to find the vulnerability of the population to possible disaster risks, in order to further integrate this data into the development of an effective community-based early warning system.

Within the framework of a joint project of the United Nations Development Programme, Ministry of Emergency Situations, and the Agency of Hydrometeorological Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan, aimed at improving of multi-hazard early warning system, it was initiated to assess the vulnerability of the population in the most hazardous areas of the country, including Kashkadarya, Samarkand, Syrdarya, Jizzak, Tashkent, Namangan, and Fergana regions.

The research was carried out by the project staff with the support of the Scientific Research Institute of Hydrometeorology and territorial subdivisions of the Ministry of Emergency

Situations. The purpose of a vulnerability assessment is to determine the likelihood of a particular threat in a given area, as well as its intensity and area of impact, and the ability of the population and infrastructure to withstand with it. Typically, the assessment begins with the identification of a potential threat - the possibility of mudflows, avalanches, landslides, and other disasters.

Primary threats can often lead to collateral or secondary threats that pose an even greater danger to the population, such as water pollution, loss of crops and livestock, destruction of socially important facilities (health centers, accidents at existing production or industrial facilities). The risk assessment, like vulnerability assessment, uses formal procedures including baseline survey, monitoring of threats and vulnerabilities, data processing, mapping, and sociological research.

The methodology of disaster risk assessment based on the survey of representative groups of population of local communities was developed based on inventory of existing methodologies and their adaptation to the conditions of Uzbekistan. The survey was conducted with participation of 1508 people from 44 local communities, 15 districts, 7 regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan. For data collection, a group was formed in each community according to the following criteria: age, gender, employment, social status, vulnerability status (disability, etc.) aspects of labor activity, according to the following:

- older people, over 60 years
- young people, 18-25 years old
- people with disabilities
- women 25 to 45 years old
- businessmen
- herders and farmers
- local police officers and representatives of local authorities
- unemployed people
- migrants who have recently returned from labor migration

All 58 questions of the survey were divided into 8 sections:

General information about respondents

Channels of access to information

Perception of natural hazards and climate change

Measures to reduce risks from natural hazards and community capacity.

Vulnerability and Sensitivity of the Population

Livelihoods and adaptation

Access to infrastructure

Resource allocation, gender equality

For better risk assessment, questions from all 8 sections have been reallocated and clustered around community adaptive capacity, community disaster preparedness, impact of hazards and vulnerability. For each of the questions, answers were prepared, which respondents chose, the answers were summarized in tables for each community and the percentage of those or other answers was calculated. In making the assessment, all groups of answers are summarized into ratios from 0 to 1 on the percentage distribution. All answers to each question were evaluated in terms of reducing or increasing the possible negative impact of the hazard. For example: if a respondent gives a positive answer to the question about the population's preparedness for disasters, i.e., he/she is ready for a disaster, has a plan of action, money, food stock, etc., this

answer goes to ‘plus’ to preparedness, other answers to ‘minus’. The overall coefficient for this question is calculated by adding positive answers and subtracting negative answers. The coefficient varies from -1 to 1. When the coefficient is closer to 1, the readiness of the population is higher (Figure 1).

Does your community have a centralised disaster warning system?					
Title of community	Unit	yes	no	Don't know	Total
Kumushkon	%	0,0	30,6	69,4	100
Istiklol	%	0,0	21,1	78,9	100
Nevich	%	0,0	17,5	82,5	100
Kizilsoy	%	0,0	23,7	76,3	100
Chinor buloq	%	0,0	31,0	69,0	100
Kungav	%	0,0	38,9	61,1	100
Koramazor	%	0,0	55,0	45,0	100
Uengilsay	%	0,0	36,6	63,4	100
Dumaloq	%	0,0	44,1	55,9	100
Kizilsuv	%	0,0	56,4	43,6	100

Figure 1. The table with comparison data of the availability of community-based early warning systems

All coefficients of one group of questions were summarized in separate tables. Similarly, the coefficients for each block were calculated. Blocks are grouped into 4 thematic groups (Figure 2). All resulting ratios are summarized in a table to calculate the risk. Spider diagrams were constructed for each question (Figure 3), block, and response group to visualize the degree of adaptability, preparedness, impact, and vulnerability of each local community.

Title of community	ADAPTABILITY	READINESS	IMPACT	VULNERABILITY	RISK
Kumushkon	0,41	0,17	0,30	0,01	0,05
Istiklol	0,48	0,23	0,28	0,02	0,05
Nevich	0,55	0,25	0,35	-0,03	-0,08
Kizilsoy	0,49	0,23	0,33	0,01	0,04
Chinor buloq	0,49	0,20	0,32	-0,12	-0,39
Kungay	0,50	0,23	0,30	-0,03	-0,09
Koramazor	0,42	0,20	0,30	0,01	0,02
Uengilsay	0,48	0,24	0,34	-0,07	-0,19
Dumaloq	0,37	0,22	0,30	-0,01	-0,03

Figure 2. Generalized Risk Analysis Table for the four baseline indicators as adaptability, readiness, impact, and vulnerability of communities.

Figure 3. The spider diagram created on results of comparison data of the availability of community-based early warning systems.

Different methods offer a variety of formulas for calculating the risk of natural disasters, in a simplified form, the formula for determining risks looks like this:

$$\text{RISK} = \text{Threat (Danger)} \times \text{Vulnerability}$$

In our case, this formula was expanded and took the form:

$$\text{RISK} = (\text{Vulnerability}) / (\text{Willingness to adapt})$$

The formula shows that the greater the population's willingness to adapt, the lower the risk. The scheme for calculating the risk of natural disasters for local communities is shown in Figure 4. In the final form of the formula, impact and vulnerability are reduced to general vulnerability, and the denominator to adaptation readiness.

$$\text{RISK} = (\text{Impact} \times \text{Vulnerability}) / (\text{Adaptability} \times \text{Readiness})$$

Figure 4. The scheme for calculating the risk of natural disasters for local communities.

Results

Based on the obtained data and spider diagrams, the most disaster-prone communities were identified and shown on the developed maps (Figures 5, 6). In our case, 5 communities (*Kumushkon, Yordon, Khovosobod, Khonim, Turkiston*) located in the territory of Syrdarya, Fergana and Kashkadarya regions of Uzbekistan were identified as the most exposed to disaster risk. Some communities do have high vulnerability in addition to high risk. At the same time, some communities in the high-risk zone have less pronounced vulnerability and their potential and ability to adapt is significantly high, given the availability of early warning systems, necessary infrastructure, and socio-economic sustainability.

But the main outcome of the conducted research, apart from identifying the communities most at risk, was to identify the communities most vulnerable to disasters, considering their inability to respond effectively to a disaster, as well as the lack of necessary early warning systems, possibility of many casualties and the development of unfavorable consequences for the population (Figures 7,8). These most vulnerable communities included 5 communities (*Buston, Yordon, Garasha, Khovosobod, Kukgumbaz*) located in Syrdarya, Fergana, Kashkadarya, Jizzak regions of

well as taking into account the heterogeneity of territorial units, geographical, social, and other conditions, alternative sources of information about the impending threat of an emergency are necessary.

Figure 7. The spider diagram on communities vulnerability assessment

Figure 8. The map of communities vulnerability

In this context, it would be advisable to have several types of warning systems in place, considering the peculiarities of a particular locality and the presence or absence of relevant infrastructure. All this together can significantly affect the vulnerability of the population, but at the same time increase its adaptability to possible threats. For example, in mountainous areas, it

will be advisable to use mobile systems for both command and control of forces and warning systems, while in densely populated areas, it will be better to use mobile systems for the management of forces and means and warning systems.

In densely populated areas, it would be better to use stationary warning systems, but with an increased radius of coverage. To reduce the level of vulnerability of the population and to ensure maximum coverage in informing the population about the emergency, these systems should be interchangeable and autonomous, so that in case of failure of one warning system or its inaccessibility, there should be an alternative to replace or automatically activate another system.

Discussion

Given the increasing climate risks, this multi-hazard early warning system will contribute to building climate resilience among the people of Uzbekistan, including the most vulnerable and poor rural communities living in mountainous areas that are currently at risk of climate change-induced hazards. An equally important direction in the development of early warning systems for emergencies is the creation of such systems at the local level, which is relevant for remote communities. In addition to the technological element of such a system, a set of measures for its implementation is proposed. These measures may include the following elements from the last 4 (fourth) component of the multi-hazard early warning system – “Readiness of population to response to forecasts and emergency warnings” [4]:

- developing a local disaster contingency plan of the community with identifying of danger zones and a scheme of evacuation routes.

- preparation of a list of residents living in the danger zones, considering vulnerable persons.

- organizing and training a group of volunteer rescuers for disaster response.

- training the population to act on alarm signals and conducting drills.

At the same time, it must be remembered that effective public information is crucial to help people understand the different types of risk and how to reduce and manage them. Moreover, people themselves can also serve as important sources of risk information for analysts and offer innovative solutions for risk management. To be most effective, public information messages must be tailored to effectively reach the entire target group, including women, girls, boys, men, the elderly, persons with disabilities and other minority groups in society, leaving no one behind.

In order to tailor messages, it is necessary to understand how women and men of different ages, abilities and backgrounds receive, process, interpret and respond to public information. This may include recognizing how gender roles and other social norms influence knowledge about disaster risks and responses to crisis information. Information messages need to be designed to be understood by the entire target group. This should consider the level of relevant knowledge among different groups, paying attention to speakers of minority languages and people with visual, hearing, and physical disabilities.

Conclusion

This research will help to build a narrative for the creation of maps of the area, mapping the most dangerous areas and territories, as well as to determine the level of vulnerability of the population living in the area. These research results will allow the Ministry of Emergency Situations to identify which communities to focus on in the context of developing a strategy for the provision of warning systems. In turn, the results of the research and mapping of the area will allow the data to be entered into the GIS software of the Ministry of Emergency Situations. This

measure will allow modelling a possible scenario of a disaster, determining the impact of the disaster on community livelihoods, selecting early warning measures, and providing estimates of possible material and social damage.

At the same time, these studies will allow the Government to make more rational use of the financial resources earmarked for the modernization of the warning systems, investing appropriately in the locations and communities required for this purpose. In general, all these activities will reduce the time for operational decision-making, thus ensuring timely notification of the population, which will ultimately contribute to reducing the number of casualties among the population and material damage caused by the disaster.

According to recent UN data, one (1) dollar invested in effective early warning systems can prevent between \$3.5 and \$20 of damage [5], which points the relevance of comprehensive development of early warning systems in the country.

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